

STRESS MANAGEMENT OF SCHOOL TEACHERS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6560128>

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Abstract: *This paper describes common features of stress for employers and specific problems faced by teachers. The focus of the discussion includes stress and the effect of stress for the teacher. After understanding all about stress and indication, it is hoped that teacher will be able to identify and diagnose it. The way to anticipate and cope with the stress is discussed in this paper.*

Keywords: *stress, reflection, transformation.*

The concept of “stress” has already firmly entered our daily lives, however, as a rule, we use this word only in a negative sense. Stress is a condition that is not always harmful. On closer examination, it helps to overcome obstacles and avoid danger. The author of the theory of stress is “a non-specific response of the body to any requirement presented to it.” Those. Stress is a universal reaction of our brain and body that helps us overcome any obstacle: illness, final exams, a decisive serve in a tennis match or an important business interview. Requirements and changes that generate stress open up two possibilities for a person:

1. Adaptation to new living conditions;
2. Potentially dangerous for a person can be too long stress or a combination of stress factors (“stressors”) that make it difficult or impossible to adapt to the requirements of the situation. The list of stressors is diverse: for simple ones such as temperature, noise, gas composition of the atmosphere, toxic substances.

CAUSES OF STRESS FOR TEACHERS In order to be able to cope with stress successfully and effectively, we need to identify its cause and the implication toward our body and daily activities. In general, the cause of stress or stressors is varied. It is much more dependent on how people perceive and respond to the stress. A particular situation or event that might cause stress for us might not work for other people. Indeed, it might be fun and pleasant. However, stress suffered by teachers at schools share common stressors. Travers and Coopers (1996) report that teachers are being stressed by the workload, the behavior of the pupils, lack of promotion prospect, unsatisfactory working conditions, poor relationship with colleagues, pupils and administrators, and a host of other problems. Kyriacou and Sutcliffe (1979) in Cooper (1996) also found similar job stressors among the teachers. Too much work to do. Asteve (1989) in Cooper (1996) prefers to divide the stressor for teacher into two parts, They are primary factors and secondary factors. Primary factors refer to things which have direct effect on the teacher in the classroom (e.g. pupil behavior,

lack of teaching resources) whereas the secondary factors refers to rapid changes over the role in the society and the increased demand placed upon teacher by the government through repeated innovation and policy. The stressors that belong to the secondary factors are:

- of the role of the teacher and of the traditional agents of social integration
- Increasing contradiction in the role of the teacher.
- Changes in the attitude of society towards the teacher.
- Uncertainty about the objectives of the education system and the furthering of knowledge.
- The deterioration of the image of the teacher

Cooper (1986b) prefers to see the causes of teacher stress from both inside and outside of work. We cannot talk only inside or outside stressors separately as they are closely related. The combinations of these two kinds of stressors are:

1. Stressors intrinsic to the actual job - i.e. Physical working condition and working load.
2. Role in the organization - i.e. role ambiguity and role conflict
3. Relationship at work
4. Career development
5. Organizational structure and climate
6. Home and work interface.

After presenting some stressors that are outlined by some experts above, I would like to relate with my own experience in dealing with stress in the school. I have worked as a teacher for 10 years, however officially I have begun my career as a teacher for the state schools or as a civil servant for 4 years. During that period of time, I have experienced and suffered stress many times. As far as my experience concerns, most of stress and pressure that I experienced were caused by primary factors such as misbehaving students in the classroom, number of students and classes that I have to teach. Misbehaving students are very stressful for me as they often create troubles in the classroom by making noises and doing as they want in the classroom. Their behaviors are not only disturbing and distracting their fellow students' concentration but also disturbing the process of teaching and learning process as a whole in the classroom. As a result, the classroom turns to be chaos and disturbing the neighboring classroom.

In general, stress on the job results in lower productivity and performance, unnecessary employee sick leave, and higher medical cost. The stress does not only affect a company or an organization but also an individual personally. How much it affects the organization and the individual is heavily depends on to what extent the individual reacts and responds to stress. For many people, Stress is always viewed as something negative and destructive. For these types of people stress will result in the low performance and motivation over the job in the office. However, there are also few people that view stress differently. They assume stress a positive thing that enhances the performance and productivity. It also could boost the motivation and spirit in the office. Wards (1993) states that everyone needs a certain level of pressure to perform well as, it provides the stimulation necessary to achieve creativity and innovation, and without sufficient pressure our performance will be restricted. On the contrary, when stress is faced with insufficient resources will become very unproductive because when we feel anxious, tense and nervous, our energy is sopped and our perspective on life becomes distorted.

CONCLUSION: Stress is a common disease suffered by employee at work including teachers. Research shows that Teachers who teach in the inner city schools suffer more stress compared to other professions. Unfortunately, Many teachers are reluctant to admit that they suffer from stress as it is often regarded as a weakness. Teacher stress is often triggered by the increased demands and responsibility placed upon them by the government and society. Ironically, the increased demands are not accompanied with sufficient resources and capability. The government still pays less attention on the teacher's feel frustrated and get stressed.

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